

Perception on the Food Service Attribute of Student-Run Food Stalls Towards Repurchase Intention: Basis for Its Continuity

Gideon D. Hombrebueno Jr^{1*}, Ma. Luisa G. Gomez^{1,2}, Christian D. Tongko^{1,3}, Glaiza G. Cabacungan^{2,4}, Ronel A. Villacruz^{3,5}, Andrea Camille D. Dela Cruz^{1,6}, Kelvin D. Bual^{1,7}, Mhandy T. Asiado^{4,8}, Eunice P. Peñaflor^{1,9}, Evelyn P. Dignadice^{1,10}, Josie C. Villaganas^{1,11}, Marlo D. Resano^{1,12} and Roel C. Ballesteros^{1,13}

¹Taguig City University

²Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Maynila

³Department of Education - Las Piñas

⁴Olivarez College - Paranaque

*gideon.hombrebueno@tcu.edu.ph, ²maluisa.gomez@tcu.edu.ph, ³christian.tongko@tcu.edu.ph

⁴ggcabacungan@plm.edu.ph, ⁵ronel.villacruz@deped.gov.ph, ⁶andreacamille.delacruz@tcu.edu.ph,

⁷kelvin.bual@tcu.edu.ph, ⁸mhandy.asiado@olivarezcollege.edu.ph, ⁹eunice.penaflor@tcu.edu.ph,

¹⁰evelyn.dignadice@tcu.edu.ph, ¹¹josie.villaganas@tcu.edu.ph, ¹²marlo.resano@tcu.edu.ph

¹³roel.ballesteros@tcu.edu.ph

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ABSTRACT

This study examined customers' perception of the food service attributes of student-run food stalls and their relationship with repurchase intention as a basis for its continuity. Anchored on the premise that food quality, service efficiency, environment, and pricing influence consumer behavior, the research employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational design. Data were collected through a survey questionnaire administered to 400 respondents. The instrument measured four dimensions of food service attributes: quality of food and beverage products, quality of service, quality of setting, and price and value, and the level of repurchase intention, all assessed using a 4-point Likert scale. Statistical tools such as weighted mean and Pearson correlation coefficient were utilized for data analysis. Findings revealed that the student-

run food stalls perform effectively across all food service dimensions. Among the attributes, quality of service ranked highest, indicating that staff behavior, efficiency, and customer interaction play a crucial role in shaping customer perceptions. This was followed by quality of setting and food quality, while price and value, although still positively rated, ranked lowest, suggesting an area for improvement. Similarly, the findings also highlighted the customers' willingness to continue purchasing due to positive experiences. Moreover, the study established a significant and strong positive relationship between food service attributes and repurchase intention indicating that improvements in service attributes directly enhance customers' likelihood to repeat patronage. The results underscore the importance of maintaining high standards in service delivery, product quality, and operational practices. Overall, the study concludes that sustaining and enhancing these attributes are essential to ensure the continuity and success of student-run food stalls as both service providers and experiential learning platforms. It was recommended as well that school administration continuously support the operation allowing student operators to be provided with hands-on experience in entrepreneurship and food service management.

Keywords: *Food Service Attribute; Food Quality; Service Quality; Student-run Food Stalls; Repurchase Intention*

INTRODUCTION

The food service industry continues to evolve as consumer expectations shift toward quality, value, and experiential dining, even within non-commercial settings such as educational institutions. School-based food services, including student-run food stalls, serve not only as support systems that provide accessible meals but also as experiential learning platforms for students pursuing hospitality-related programs. According to Fernandez (2025), non-commercial food service operations are primarily cost-oriented and exist to support institutional objectives rather than profit generation. In recent years, increasing competition and evolving consumer expectations have emphasized the importance of delivering high-quality food, efficient service, and favorable dining environments. Studies show that food service operations must continuously enhance service quality and customer experience to sustain patronage and remain competitive (Salsabila, 2023). Moreover, repurchase intention has emerged as a crucial indicator of customer loyalty and long-term business sustainability, reflecting customers' willingness to repeatedly avail of a service based on prior experience (Elbanna et al., 2022). In the context of school-based food stall services, these factors are equally significant as they directly influence students' and staff's dining choices.

Existing literature suggests that food service attributes significantly influence subsequent behavioral intentions. For instance, research by Ellitan and Edgar (2024) found that both food quality and service quality have a direct and significant influence on customer satisfaction, which in turn positively affects repurchase intention. Similarly, Firdaus et al. (2023) emphasized that service quality plays a critical role in shaping repurchase intention, particularly when mediated by customer satisfaction. In addition, pricing strategies and perceived value have been identified as strong determinants of repeat purchase behavior, especially in food-related industries where consumers are highly sensitive to cost and quality alignment (Suryani et al., 2024). These findings highlight that multiple dimensions of service collectively influence whether customers choose to return.

However, despite the growing body of research on food service quality and consumer behavior, there remains limited empirical investigations focusing specifically on student-operated food stalls within academic institutions. Most existing studies concentrate on commercial restaurants or large-scale food service operations, which differ significantly from student-managed stalls in terms of resources, experience, and operational consistency. For example, while studies in the Philippine context confirm that service quality strongly influences customer satisfaction and repurchase intention in restaurants (Cordova et al., 2024), these findings may not fully capture the dynamics present in student-operated food stalls. Additionally, the unique nature of student-run food stalls, where operators are still developing their skills, may influence service consistency and customer perceptions differently compared to professional establishments. This gap highlights the need for a contextualized examination of how food service attributes affect repurchase intention in this specific setting, particularly within local university environments.

In response to these gaps, the present study aims to assess customers' perception on the food service attributes of student-run food stalls and examine their relationship with repurchase intention. This study seeks to provide empirical evidence that can inform improvements in operational practices and contribute to the sustainability of such initiatives. By identifying key factors that influence repurchase intention, the findings of this study will offer practical recommendations for enhancing food service attributes and ensuring the continuity of the student-run food stalls.

METHODS

The aim of this study was to assess the perception of the customers on the food service attributes of the student-run food stalls towards their repurchase intention. Therefore, this research utilized a quantitative research approach, specifically descriptive-correlational research design, which provided an essential knowledge on the assessment of the given variables, as well as their relationship. This design helped explore the existing connections

between these variables under the given conditions, making it the most appropriate approach for this study. Data was collected through a structured survey questionnaire that was distributed to the customers of the student-run food stalls. The target population of this study includes all teaching and non-teaching personnel, as well as the students of Taguig City University. This research used a non-probability sampling method, specifically convenience sampling technique, wherein a total of 400 customers was selected to participate in the study. Respondents was chosen based on their voluntary participation.

This study utilized a researcher-made instrument that gathered the necessary information and data from the customers. The survey questionnaire underwent pilot testing and reliability analysis among 30 respondents, yielding a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.9162, which was interpreted as having excellent internal consistency. The research instrument consisted of the following parts: Part I assessed the perception of the customers on the food service attribute of the student-run food stalls in terms of quality of food and beverage products with 5 indicators, quality of service with 5 indicators, quality of setting with 5 indicators, and price and value with 5 indicators, in which it was all evaluated using a 4-Point Likert Scale with the given scoring and interpretation: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1); and Part II determined the customers' level of repurchase intention with 8 indicators, in which it was also evaluated using a 4-Point Likert Scale with the given scoring and interpretation: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). The survey questionnaire has undergone validation process which included consulting with experts on the appropriateness of the instrument. The data gathered were then tabulated, interpreted, analyzed, and processed using the following statistical tools: Weighted Mean was used to evaluate the mean scores of the responses on each item in terms of the food service attribute and the level of repurchase intention; and Pearson Correlation Coefficient was used to test the relationship between the food service attributes of the student-run food stalls and the customers' level of repurchase intention.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1. *Perception of the Customers on the Food Service Attributes of the Student-run Food Stalls in terms of Quality of Food and Beverage Products*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The menu items offered match my meal needs and preferences.	3.70	Strongly Agree	2
2. The food products maintain consistent taste and portion across visits.	3.65	Strongly Agree	5
3. The stalls introduce new or locally inspired dishes that makes me want to try them.	3.68	Strongly Agree	3
4. The stalls provide clear, attractive options for healthier choices.	3.67	Strongly Agree	4
5. The actual product meets the expectations set by its description.	3.71	Strongly Agree	1
Average Weighted Mean	3.68	Strongly Agree	

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree), 2.50-3.49 (Agree), 1.50-2.49 (Disagree), and 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 1 presents the perception of the customers on the food service attributes of the student-run food stalls in terms of quality of food and beverage products with an average weighted mean of 3.68 and interpreted as Strongly Agree. This suggest that the stalls are generally successful in meeting customer expectations in terms of product quality, variety, and overall satisfaction.

Among the indicators, "*The actual product meets the expectations set by its description*" ranked the highest which implies that customers perceive honesty and reliability in how food items are presented, which is critical factor in building trust and repeat patronage. Meanwhile, though still rated as strongly agree, the indicator "*The food products maintain consistent taste and portion across visits*" ranked the lowest indicating that while customers are generally satisfied, this result highlights a minor area for improvement.

These findings are supported by the study of Ling et al. (2024) and Prasai (2026) emphasizing that food quality, particularly taste, freshness, and presentation, plays a crucial role in attracting and retaining customers. Furthermore, the study of Zandi et al. (2025) stated that the availability of new or locally inspired dishes and healthier options shows that innovation and health-conscious offerings contribute positively to customer perception and satisfaction. However, Zhang (2025) noted that inconsistent food quality can negatively affect customer trust and satisfaction as variations in taste and portion lead to dissatisfaction.

Table 2. *Perception of the Customers on the Food Service Attributes of the Student-run Food Stalls in terms of Quality of Service*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The stall staff are polite and make the ordering experience pleasant.	3.81	Strongly Agree	1
2. The ordering and payment process at the stalls is smooth and time-efficient.	3.80	Strongly Agree	2
3. The staff present themselves in a clean, professional manner that builds my trust.	3.79	Strongly Agree	3
4. The staff demonstrates competence in preparing and serving the menu items.	3.74	Strongly Agree	4.5
5. The food is prepared and delivered within an acceptable waiting time.	3.74	Strongly Agree	4.5
Average Weighted Mean	3.78	Strongly Agree	

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree), 2.50-3.49 (Agree), 1.50-2.49 (Disagree), and 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 2 shows the perception of the customers on the food service attributes of the student-run food stalls in terms of quality of service with an average weighted mean of 3.78 and interpreted as Strongly Agree. This indicates that the service dimension of the food stalls meets customer expectations in multiple aspects and suggest that customers perceive the service as efficient, reliable, and customer-oriented.

Among the indicators, “*The stall staff are polite and make the ordering experience pleasant*” ranked first which implies that interpersonal skills and customer interaction are the strongest aspects of service delivery. On the other hand, the indicators “*The staff demonstrates competence in preparing and serving the menu items*” and “*The food is prepared and delivered within an acceptable waiting time*” ranked slightly lower but still fall within the “strongly agree” range which shows that while these areas are still positively perceived, there may be minor opportunities for improvement, particularly in enhancing speed and consistency during peak hours.

These findings are supported by the study of Abdulrab and Hezam (2024) emphasizing that service quality dimensions such as responsiveness, empathy, and assurance is a fundamental determinant of satisfaction and loyalty in hospitality settings and shape how customers evaluate service experience. In addition, the study of Puspitarini (2025) found that staff friendliness and positive interaction are among the most important contributors which highlighted that friendly staff behavior significantly enhances customer experience and encourages repeat patronage.

Table 3. *Perception of the Customers on the Food Service Attributes of the Student-run Food Stalls in terms of Quality of Setting*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The student-run food stalls are conveniently located relative to classes and common areas.	3.73	Strongly Agree	2
2. The stall opening times fit my class schedule and typical meal times.	3.65	Strongly Agree	4
3. The seating and immediate environment around the stalls are comfortable enough to eat there.	3.62	Strongly Agree	5

4. It is easy to find the stalls and know what each one offers.	3.75	Strongly Agree	1
5. The appearance of the stall and counters is clean and well.	3.72	Strongly Agree	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.69	Strongly Agree	

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree), 2.50-3.49 (Agree), 1.50-2.49 (Disagree), and 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 3 discusses the perception of the customer on the food service attributes of the student-run food stalls in terms of quality of setting with an average weighted mean of 3.69 and interpreted as Strongly Agree. This suggests that the physical environment, accessibility, and overall arrangement of the stalls effectively meet the needs and expectations of customers.

Among the indicators, *“It is easy to find the stalls and know what each one offers”* ranked the highest which implies that visibility, signage, and stall organization are well-managed, allowing customers to quickly identify food options. Meanwhile, while still positively rated, *“The seating and immediate environment around the stalls are comfortable enough to eat there”* received a relatively lower ranking suggesting that minor areas for improvement in enhancing dining spaces are more responsive to the customers.

These findings are supported by the study of James et al. (2024) stating that elements such as interior and exterior signage and menu presentation significantly influence customer satisfaction, as they help customers easily navigate the service environment and understand available offerings. Similarly, research by Guntur and Indrawati (2025) highlighted that servicescape elements, including signs and functional layout, contribute to satisfaction which positively affect customer experience and revisit intention. Furthermore, Chua et al. (2020) also found that accessibility and proximity influence customers’ decisions, as convenient locations enhance ease of access and encourage repeat patronage.

Table 4. *Perception of the Customers on the Food Service Attributes of the Student-run Food Stalls in terms of Price and Value*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The prices are affordable for a student budget.	3.61	Strongly Agree	4
2. The prices charged reflects the quality and portion I received.	3.62	Strongly Agree	3
3. Prices are clearly displayed and easy to understand before I order.	3.75	Strongly Agree	1
4. The stalls offer items across different price range to suit my budget.	3.68	Strongly Agree	2
5. Occasional discounts, combos, or student promotions are available from the food stalls.	3.55	Strongly Agree	5
Average Weighted Mean	3.64	Strongly Agree	

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree), 2.50-3.49 (Agree), 1.50-2.49 (Disagree), and 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 4 illustrates the perception of the customers on the food service attributes of the student-run food stalls in terms of price and value with an average weighted mean of 3.64 and interpreted as Strongly Agree. This indicates that the customers generally perceive the pricing strategies of these stalls as fair, reasonable, and aligned with their financial capacity as affordable remains a key factor which reinforces the importance of cost-conscious offerings in campus-based food services.

Among the indicators, *“Prices are clearly displayed and easy to understand before I order”* ranked first suggesting that transparency plays a crucial role and when prices are clearly shown and easy to understand before ordering, customers feel more confident and comfortable making purchasing decisions. On the other hand, although it still falls within the “strongly agree” category, *“Occasional discounts, combos, or student promotions are available from the food stalls”* ranked the lowest which implies that while promotional offers are present, there may be room for improvement in making them more frequent or attractive to further enhance perceived value.

These findings are supported by the study of Konuk (2023) emphasizing that price transparency significantly improves customer trust and satisfaction, especially in food service settings where customers make quick purchase decision, and when prices are clearly displayed, customers experience less uncertainty and perceive the service as more reliable. In addition, the study of Han and Hyun (2022) found that offering a range of price options allows food establishments to cater to diverse customer segments, increasing received value and overall satisfaction. Furthermore, Tan et al. (2025) also found that price fairness is strongly influenced by the balance between perceived quality and the actual price paid, emphasizing that customers evaluate whether what they receive matches what they pay.

Table 5. Composite Table of the Food Service Attributes of the Student-run Food Stalls

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Quality of Food and Beverage Products	3.68	Strongly Agree	3
2. Quality of Service	3.78	Strongly Agree	1
3. Quality of Setting	3.69	Strongly Agree	2
4. Price and Value	3.64	Strongly Agree	4
Overall Weighted Mean	3.70	Strongly Agree	

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree), 2.50-3.49 (Agree), 1.50-2.49 (Disagree), and 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 5 presents the composite table of the food service attributes of the student-run food stalls with an overall weighted mean of 3.70 and interpreted as Strongly Agree. This suggests that the stalls are effectively meeting customer expectations across multiple dimensions of the food service attributes.

Among the four indicators, “*Quality of Service*” ranked the highest which implies that staff behavior, efficiency, and interaction with customers play a crucial role in shaping repeat patronage. The strong performance in this area suggests that the student-run food stalls are successful in maintaining courteous, responsive, and customer-oriented service practices. On the other hand, “*Price and Value*” received the lowest rank, although it is still interpreted as “strongly agree,” means that while customers generally find the pricing acceptable, it is the least strong aspect among the four indicators. This may imply that there is room for improvement in ensuring that customers perceive the prices as fully aligned with the quality and quantity of food and service provided.

These overall findings are aligned with the study of Crossman (2024) stating that service quality significantly influences satisfaction and loyalty, specifically, dimensions such as responsiveness, reliability, and employee interaction strongly shape customer perceptions. Moreover, Yang et al. (2025) emphasized that dimensions such as interaction quality and physical setting jointly affect behavioral intentions. Shyju et al. (2021) also highlighted that satisfaction and repurchase intention is closely tied to perceived value and overall service experience.

Table 6. Level of Repurchase Intention on the Student-run Food Stalls

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I believe buying food again from the student-run stalls would be a good choice for my daily meals.	3.68	Strongly Agree	5
2. Reordering from the student-run food stalls will give me a satisfying and dependable experience.	3.65	Strongly Agree	6.5
3. Most of the people frequently purchase from the student-run stalls, and that makes me more likely to repurchase too.	3.65	Strongly Agree	6.5
4. Even if a stall is crowded or a popular item is low on stock, I can usually find an alternative and still repurchase there.	3.62	Strongly Agree	8
5. I am willing to support the student-run food stalls because they offer fair prices and quality.	3.73	Strongly Agree	2

6. I intend to continue buying food from the student-run food stalls because of the good experience I've encountered.	3.71	Strongly Agree	3
7. The staff's welcoming atmosphere encourages me to visit and purchase again.	3.74	Strongly Agree	1
8. I am more likely to purchase again because the actual products meet my expectations set by its description.	3.70	Strongly Agree	4
Overall Weighted Mean	3.70	Strongly Agree	

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree), 2.50-3.49 (Agree), 1.50-2.49 (Disagree), and 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 6 shows the level of repurchase intention on the student-run food stalls with an overall weighted mean of 3.70 and interpreted as Strongly Agree. This suggest that customers generally have positive experience that translate into a willingness to buy again, reinforcing the idea that satisfaction plays a crucial role in repeat purchasing behavior.

Among the indicators, *“The staff's welcoming atmosphere encourages me to visit and purchase again”* ranked the highest which highlights the importance of interpersonal service in influencing customer loyalty and implies as well that beyond food quality, the way customers are treated significantly affects their intention to return. Meanwhile, while still rated positively, *“Even if a stall is crowded or a popular item is low on stock, I can usually find an alternative and still repurchase there”* ranked slightly lower which suggests that even situational challenges such as crowding or limited stock did not significantly deter repurchase intention indicating a generally resilient customer preference for these stalls.

These findings are supported by the study of Gucal and Gurbuz (2024) confirming that service quality is significantly associated with customer loyalty and repurchase intention, which justifies that better service leads to stronger repeat purchase behavior. Additionally, the recent study of Jibrán et al. (2025) highlighting the mediating role of customer satisfaction between service quality and repurchase intention, reinforcing that better service leads to repeat purchasing through satisfaction.

Table 7. *Relationship Between the Perception of the Customers on the Food Service Attributes of the Student-run Food Stalls and their Level of Repurchase Intention*

Indicators	r	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Food Service Attributes	0.6254	Strong Correlation	<0.0001	Reject Ho	Significant
Level of Repurchase Intention					

If p-value <0.05 significance, reject Ho. Otherwise, accept.

As illustrated in Table 7, the test of significant relationship between the perception of the customer on the food service attributes of the student-run food stalls and their level of repurchase intention obtained a Pearson r value of 0.6254 which shows a strong correlation. Furthermore, the test also revealed a p-value of <0.0001 which significantly lower than the 0.05 level which resulted in the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that the greater the food service attributes, the higher the level of repurchase intention.

These findings are aligned with the study of Chen et al. (2021) stating that service quality and food quality are strongly correlated with customer satisfaction, which in turn has a very strong correlation with repurchase intention. Moreover, the study of Wu et al. (2024) also demonstrated that multiple dimensions of service quality such as reliability, assurance, and food quality significantly increase reuse intention in food service. Furthermore, the study of Ellitan and Edgar (2024) found that both food quality and service quality, which are key components of food service attributes, have a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention, which emphasized that improved service delivery directly increases customers' likelihood of returning.

CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of the study indicate that student-run food stalls are generally effective in delivering food service attributes that align with customer expectations, thereby supporting its operational continuity. In terms of product-related factors, the stalls demonstrate strong performance in quality, variety, and overall satisfaction, suggesting that customers are consistently receiving offerings that meet their preferences. This positive perception is further reinforced by the service dimension, where efficiency, reliability, and customer-oriented practices are evident. Moreover, the physical environment and accessibility of the stalls are perceived to be well-organized and convenient, enabling customers to easily engage with the services provided. Pricing also emerges as a critical strength, as customers view the cost of food items as fair and aligned with their financial capacity. These positive perceptions across multiple food service attributes translate into high levels of customer satisfaction, which in turn foster a strong willingness to repurchase. As improvements in product quality, service delivery, environment, and pricing directly contribute to increased repurchase intention, sustaining and refining these factors is essential. This contributes to the growing body of knowledge on non-commercial food service by demonstrating that service quality remains the most influential factor even in student-managed environments.

In light of the discussion above, it was recommended that student operators continuously maintain and improve food quality and menu variation by considering customer preferences and ensuring consistency in preparation and presentation. Utilization of standardized recipes, standard operating procedures, and implementation of portion control guidelines to ensure consistency in food quality and preparation across different operators was also recommended. Improving stall cleanliness, organization, and visual appeal should remain a priority to create a more inviting and accessible environment for customers. Adopting fair and student-friendly pricing strategies is essential. Regular review of pricing in relation to costs and students' financial capacity will help sustain affordability while maintaining product value. Establishing a simple and accessible feedback mechanism, such as suggestion forms or digital surveys, is encouraged to better understand customer needs and continuously improve service delivery. For the school administration, it is recommended to institutionalize and continuously support the operation of the student-run food stalls as part of experiential learning or practicum programs. Allowing student operators to manage and sustain these stalls over time will provide them with hands-on experience in entrepreneurship and food service management, while ensuring the continuity and consistent improvement of stall operations. Improvement of infrastructure and provision of adequate space, utilities, and facilities for the food stalls will help ensure a safe, organized, and efficient operational environment. For other schools, the findings of this study may serve as a basis for implementing or improving their own student-run food stall program by emphasizing the importance of quality, service efficiency, affordability, and customer satisfaction. Adopting similar monitoring and evaluation practices can help assess food service performance and strengthen student entrepreneurship initiatives within campus settings. Finally, for future researchers, it was recommended to explore additional variables such as customer loyalty, marketing strategies, or digital ordering systems to further understand factors influencing repurchase intention. Conducting comparative studies across different institutions may provide more comprehensive insights and strengthen the generalization of findings related to student-run food stall operations.

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